

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Soza****FIRST NAME: Soledad****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied U.S. conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did not use Zotero to insert references

The author used Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: Microsoft Word 365 on Windows 10

1. Essay Writing (EUCLID 2019, 1-4)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5-6)
3. Achieving "Logical Flow" (EUCLID 2019, 13)
4. Stay Focused (EUCLID 2019, 14)
5. Literature Review (EUCLID 2019, 17)
6. American versus British English (EUCLID 2019, 27-29)
7. Chicago Manual of Style (EUCLID 2019, 44-55)

LINGUISTIC, SCHOLARLY, AND ETHICAL INTERLINKAGES IN DOCTORAL WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

I have been working as a Professor of International Relations after a 10-year experience as an English teacher for students from all walks-of-life. In both strands, I have been confronted with three challenges in academic work: linguistic approaches, scholarly habits, and ethical perspectives. These three elements are interconnected and overlap in terms of fulfilling my duties in the classroom and guiding students' papers. I have been much impressed by the quality of the material in the ACA-401 period one (1) material and the course video's pedagogical feature. This course encompasses the three above mentioned interlinkages in doctoral writing. As a student commencing this endeavor in completing a Ph.D. at EUCLID, paper essay will pose challenges in the following terms:

1. Linguistic criteria needed to comply with the grammar rules, morpho-syntactic alignments, punctuation, and spelling
2. Scholarly approaches to align the essay question with supporting theories and empirical evidence in any given field

3. Ethics of rigor, honesty, thoroughness, and accuracy at Ph.D. level

Therefore, the ACA-401 period one (1) material is an important subject area that connects the linguistic dimension, the scholarly mindset, and the ethical aspects, which are intertwined in Ph.D. research and essay writing. These three aspects are conveyed efficiently in a clear, pedagogical manner in the ACA-401 material throughout the chapters. I have encapsulated the main elements in seven (7) concepts listed above.

2) SUMMARY OF THE MATERIAL

The ACA-401 period one material offers the student a comprehensive, pedagogical, and in-depth guide on writing for academic purposes. The material is organized into nine (9) chapters, all sequenced and interrelated. Material ranges from the broad discussion on essay questions, the central thesis and topic research in the initial Chapter to the differences in American and British English in Chapter 6, the ACA-401 material strikes me as a novel, helpful, and clarifying manual. In that particular area, the ACA-401 coursepack gives special attention to punctuation, syntax, and grammar when using English for academic purposes.

The chapters are well-organized. They appropriately fulfill the objectives, from generalizations to specific details, cautioning the student to include the formal aspects of writing and literature review. The seven main concepts in the ACA-401 period one (1) material, such as essay writing, plagiarism, logical flow, staying focused, literature review, the American versus British English, and the Chicago Manual of Style, are consistently reinforced throughout the course material. The ACA-401 coursepack is both helpful and reassuring for any student seeking to learn in distance mode. The chapters also convey extensive advice and guidance for citing and referencing through fine examples. Finally, the material cautions the student that some mistakes or errors appear uncorrected intentionally to raise the student's awareness on language use, which I could personally verify in the section "essay paragraphs" (EUCLID 2019, 3) from the course material. This exercise serves as a sample of self-discovery and pedagogical tools.

3) REACTION TO THE MATERIAL

It is my view after reading the ACA-401 period one (1) material that the linguistic dimension, scholarly habits, and the ethical preoccupation with high-quality academic output, in preparation for thesis writing, are in effect interconnected. Therefore, I will discuss the interconnection of the three dimensions outlined in the INTRODUCTION in a dialogue with the seven (7) main topics from the ACA-401 material, which are listed above. In the following discussion, I will explore how the three dimensions reinforce one another through an interdependency link. To prove my point, I will also attempt to demonstrate that these interlinkages are, in fact, explicitly stated in the ACA-401 material by way of exhibiting the convergence of these three dimensions with the seven concepts from ACA-401 coursepack above-mentioned.

a) Essay Writing or Essay Disciplinarian?

In connection to “essay writing” (EUCLID 2019, 1-4), the ACA-401 period one (1) material displays step-by-step guidance by emphasizing the importance of brainstorming, organizing ideas around the main thesis, and having a plan to which to return to achieve sophistication as stated in the ACA-401 material. In that regard, “essay writing” in six steps (EUCLID 2019, 1-4) lays out valuable advice for organizing ideas, putting them aside for a day or two, and getting back to the original to make changes accordingly to find a suitable essay question and the main essay thesis. These steps are indeed vital in thesis writing. They are an integral part of the set of scholarly habits required on the part of the student seeking to ensure that the central thesis is aligned to the bibliography available in the field or the theories supporting the research area. In that regard, it has been inevitable to recall the disciplinarian training I received in the Research Methods Course in the MSc Political Science course by highlighting that the main thesis and the research question(s) are inextricably linked to the literary corpus available in the field. In sum, the theoretical framework and the empirical evidence supporting such theories are bi-directional. According to King, Keohane, and Verba (1994), the data will support the theories, and the theories will feed the data. In devising the essay question and the main thesis of the research project, a Ph.D. student should carry out an extensive and thorough revision of the field’s literature before devising the project. By revising the different theories available in the topic area and the literary corpus supporting the various hypothesis, theories, and models, a valuable Ph.D. research project will be more viable in the long run. Thus, the task of literature review should be carried out in advance. The essay question should incorporate a novel aspect to add to the scholarly community, one which has been neglected or overlooked in previous research. It can provide insight into a missed angle from the theory, or it can present the need for new reformulations, all of which might strengthen the available views, or it can help to falsify the theoretical framework. Therefore, in the words of King, Keohane, and Verba (1994), the research design must be formulated within the existing literature available in a particular field. This aspect is explicitly stated in the ACA-401 coursepack (EUCLID 2019, 2; 17).

b) Plagiarism and Scholarly Habits

At Ph.D. level, in designing the project and devising the research question and the topic, any social scientist must bear in mind that the theory feeding the data and the data supporting the theory, is bi-directional (King, Keohane, and Verba 1994). This element compels the scientist to carry out extensive reading in the research area to envisage what his/her contribution should be to the field. There are two criteria that any researcher in the social design should fulfill. First, “a research project should pose a question that is *‘important’* in the real world” (King, Keohane, and Verba 1994, 15). This aspect is captured in the ACA-401 material by indicating that “researching provides the knowledge and evidence that allows you to develop a thesis and argument to answer the essay question” (EUCLID 2019, 2).

The ACA-401 course material signals that “a feature of most academic writing is that it draws on the work of other writers and researchers (EUCLID 2019, 2). Scholarly habits also interlink with ethics, placing any social scientist or Ph.D. student for this matter with the task of properly citing and referencing to add consistency and “logical flow” (EUCLID 2019, 13) to his/her work. In that regard, the ACA-401 material provides extensive guidance on the Chicago Style Manual (EUCLID 2019, 44-55), together with instructions on resorting to Zotero to facilitate harmonious referencing. These tools and advice in the ACA-401 coursepack exhibit a strong argument against plagiarism and proper citing.

Secondly, “a project should make a specific contribution to an identifiable scholarly literature by increasing our collective ability to construct verified scientific explanations of some aspects of the world” (King, Keohane, and Verba 1994, 15). This is also well captured by the ACA-401 material by providing the student with guiding questions such as “what do I really know about the topic?” or “what do I need to read to be able to answer the essay question?” (EUCLID 2019, 2). These questions will prompt the student to return to his essay plan to make sure that the academic essay is in effect including important examples and supporting empirical data from credible authors as clearly explained on page one (1) from Chapter 1, “Essay Writing”, in the ACA-401 material.

c) Why the Logical Flow is both Linguistic and Scholarly?

At Ph.D. level, coherence and cohesion are vital to achieve the “logical flow” (EUCLID 2019, 13) that is emphasized in the ACA-401 material, but not only by using connectors such as “therefore” or “however” (EUCLID 2019, 13). Connectors refer to language cohesion, while coherence relates to ensuring that the essay question and the central thesis will be aligned to the theoretical foundations by immersing into the research area and reading extensively in the field and in advance.

Coherence can be achieved by rigorous adherence to the two criteria explained by King, Keohane, and Verba (1994), discussed in the preceding paragraphs, and which are conveyed in the ACA-401 course material. Cohesion, in turn, refers to the use of grammatical tools such as connectors juxtaposing sub-ideas by joining them through causality, addition, contradiction, or time sequence adding consistency to the main thesis. These connectors, such as nevertheless, therefore, or moreover, among others, introduce the new paragraph containing a new minor idea and thus will prepare the reader for the emphasis effect that the author is seeking by reinforcing or contradicting a preceding sub-idea. Generally, the use of the connector “in addition” will reinforce a previously mentioned minor idea pointing to the main thesis. To oppose the preceding views, generally the use of the connector “however” is introduced to assess a previously mentioned sub-idea critically. These connectors are effective in achieving cohesion and pertain to the realm of linguistic tools in the grammar corpus (Christian 2019)

Therefore, achieving the logical flow in essay writing, it is fair to admit that both linguistic and scholarly approaches are needed to achieve the goal of logic and sequencing. Consequently, I observe there is an interconnection of approaches between linguistic skills

and scholarly habits, which I am inclined to emphasize as inseparable, and this connection is properly interlinked with the concepts discussed in the ACA-401 course material.

d) English use in academic settings

English is - generally speaking - the *lingua franca* for official communications in multicultural settings and fora; therefore, writing in English for academic purposes poses challenges regarding language command and effective communication, particularly for non-native English speakers. International students pursuing a Ph.D. will be tasked with the art of domineering the language at a proficient level to submit papers for peer revision, publication, and conferences. Mastering the art depends on motivational and cognitive variables (Gardner 2010) involved in the formal process of learning English as a second language. Nonetheless, regardless of one's mother tongue, humans all born with in-built devices in the brain to be cognizant of the material world in which we live (Chomsky 1969). There are objects in the real world, objects have features, and humans realize actions in various modes. Mastering the art to attain a nearly native command of English can be a great task, one which is a life-long challenge. Theorists in cross-linguistic approaches (Robinson 2008) explain that our command of Language 2 - in this case, English - will significantly depend on our command of Language 1 or mother tongue. Consequently, I am pleased that ACA-401 period one (1) coursepack provides international students with unique explanations, examples, valuable guiding, and appropriate warning in gray areas such as "American versus British English" (EUCLID 2019, 27-29) in terms of spelling as well as punctuation. In that sense, I was also pleased to review the extensive examples in "different spelling, although same pronunciation" (EUCLID 2019, 28), such as *axe* versus *ax*, for that matter.

Moreover, EUCLID makes extensive use of technological tools such as Grammarly as well as EUCLID's official Word templates to achieve standardized and harmonized communications in a very orderly fashion. Additionally, the Instructor of the ACA-401 period one course offers valuable support and guidance, specifically in drafting the RPI for this coursepack. Mastering the art of academic writing – and *in English* - stands out as an essential factor when submitting a paper to international journals as the standards will be higher in PhD training than in MSc. degree courses in terms of academic output attuned to English use attuned to scholarly habits and ethical commitments to high quality work.

4) CONCLUSION

I deem necessary to conclude that writing in English for academic purposes is a daunting challenge. The task requires skills pertaining to the linguistic arena, scholarly training in academic rigor and approaches, and draws on ethical dimensions. These three factors converge in a three-dimensional level capturing the seven (7) above mentioned concepts involved in thesis writing as depicted and explained in the ACA-401 material. Suffice to say that I am pleased to confirm my apprehensions about embarking on a Ph.D. degree course. In that sense, I will have to agree with King, Keohane & Verba (1995), who rely on the words of the physicist Richard Feynman (1965) by affirming that no matter how

beautiful my essay writing may appear to be or sound, if it is not based on evidence or if it contradicts the empirical findings, then my guess is wrong, and it should be discarded. This requirement also applies to any well-established research thesis; if it is poorly written, lacking in linguistic fundamentals in the English use, although brilliantly researched, it will remain as incomprehensible as in the former case.

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